

Descriptives - Motivation facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	19	.6789	.16948	.03888	.4972	.6606	.21	1.00
	Tim	31	.5653	.27842	.05001	.4632	.6674	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.5705	.24095	.03408	.5020	.6389	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	19	.6309	.26384	.06053	.5037	.7581	.10	1.00
	Tim	31	.6841	.31031	.05573	.5703	.7980	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6639	.29191	.04128	.5809	.7469	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	19	.5662	.16563	.03800	.4863	.6460	.14	.80
	Tim	31	.5812	.24679	.04433	.4907	.6717	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.5755	.21777	.03080	.5136	.6374	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	19	1484.7895	774.09830	177.59033	1111.6860	1857.8929	783.00	2605.00
	Tim	31	1168.4516	568.97820	102.19150	959.7487	1377.1545	543.00	2650.00
	Total	50	1288.6600	665.12256	94.06254	1099.6343	1477.6857	543.00	2650.00
FirstActDet	Abby	19	159.6842	135.97428	31.19464	94.1467	225.2217	50.00	540.00
	Tim	31	171.9032	128.57095	23.09203	124.7430	219.0634	50.00	455.00
	Total	50	167.2600	130.18634	18.41113	130.2615	204.2585	50.00	540.00
LastActDet	Abby	19	1189.8421	874.13947	200.54135	768.5204	1611.1638	246.00	2600.00
	Tim	31	799.7419	443.16438	79.59467	637.1879	962.2959	234.00	2005.00
	Total	50	947.9800	661.45565	93.54395	759.9964	1135.9636	234.00	2600.00
ProcDur	Abby	19	294.9474	264.94622	60.78283	167.2474	422.6474	5.00	985.00
	Tim	31	368.7097	265.02770	47.60038	271.4967	465.9226	1.00	1072.00
	Total	50	340.6800	264.76100	37.44286	265.4358	415.9242	1.00	1072.00
FixRel	Abby	19	1.6613	.64792	.14864	1.3490	1.9736	.65	2.60
	Tim	31	1.5527	.65012	.11676	1.3142	1.7912	.50	2.60
	Total	50	1.5940	.64484	.09119	1.4107	1.7772	.50	2.60
FixIrrel	Abby	19	3.6223	3.92992	.90159	1.7281	5.5164	.06	15.20
	Tim	31	4.2990	4.61705	.82925	2.6055	5.9926	.06	15.20
	Total	50	4.0419	4.33991	.61376	2.8085	5.2753	.06	15.20
AvDurRelFix	Abby	19	482.6341	367.70546	84.35742	305.4057	659.8624	120.29	1567.33
	Tim	31	477.6418	354.29105	63.63255	347.6868	607.5968	47.00	1417.86
	Total	50	479.5389	355.70251	50.30393	378.4493	580.6284	47.00	1567.33
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	19	705.2547	460.68738	105.68893	483.2105	927.2989	180.07	1817.39
	Tim	31	563.9818	457.49256	82.16809	396.1722	731.7914	26.48	1642.04
	Total	50	617.6655	459.24251	64.94670	487.1502	748.1808	26.48	1817.39
TotSac	Abby	19	59.4211	11.65388	2.67358	53.8041	65.0380	43.00	79.00
	Tim	31	61.0968	12.36488	2.22080	56.5613	65.6322	40.00	79.00
	Total	50	60.4600	12.00716	1.69807	57.0476	63.8724	40.00	79.00
Sac2Key	Abby	19	27.4211	7.98830	1.83264	23.5708	31.2713	15.00	47.00
	Tim	31	30.3871	11.44167	2.05498	26.1903	34.5839	15.00	55.00
	Total	50	29.2600	10.28137	1.45401	26.3381	32.1819	15.00	55.00
AvAttention	Abby	19	.6368	.18622	.04272	.5471	.7266	.30	.90
	Tim	31	.6839	.20016	.03595	.6105	.7573	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6660	.19442	.02750	.6107	.7213	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	19	.6895	.20520	.04708	.5906	.7884	.30	1.00
	Tim	31	.6839	.19849	.03565	.6111	.7567	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6860	.19899	.02814	.6294	.7426	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	19	.3632	.16059	.03684	.2858	.4406	.10	.60
	Tim	31	.4065	.14591	.02621	.3529	.4600	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3900	.15152	.02143	.3469	.4331	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	19	788.9474	148.61190	34.09391	717.3187	860.5760	503.00	954.00
	Tim	31	779.5806	136.25681	24.47245	729.6012	829.5600	510.00	998.00
	Total	50	783.1400	139.64606	19.74893	743.4530	822.8270	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	19	46.7439	20.46743	4.69555	36.8789	56.6089	22.41	82.27
	Tim	31	42.4568	21.54265	3.86917	34.5549	50.3587	10.92	82.27
	Total	50	44.6003	21.00504	3.28236	35.7174	53.4838	16.66	82.27

	Total	50	44.0859	21.03426	2.97469	38.1080	50.0637	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	19	28.9752	19.37207	4.44426	19.6382	38.3123	2.81	53.31
	Tim	31	25.2099	20.59451	3.69888	17.6557	32.7640	.10	60.08
	Total	50	26.6407	20.02347	2.83175	20.9501	32.3313	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	19	74.2105	13.04513	2.99276	67.9230	80.4981	50.00	90.00
	Tim	31	76.7742	18.82146	3.38043	69.8704	83.6780	20.00	100.00
	Total	50	75.8000	16.76245	2.37057	71.0362	80.5638	20.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	19	24.2105	22.25254	5.10508	13.4851	34.9359	5.00	65.00
	Tim	31	28.7097	22.02149	3.95518	20.6321	36.7872	5.00	70.00
	Total	50	27.0000	21.99258	3.11022	20.7498	33.2502	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	19	41.5789	20.88677	4.79175	31.5118	51.6460	5.00	90.00
	Tim	31	47.0968	28.94749	5.19912	36.4788	57.7148	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	45.0000	26.08855	3.68948	37.5857	52.4143	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	19	52.3684	29.55073	6.77940	38.1254	66.6114	5.00	100.00
	Tim	31	51.2903	33.66422	6.04627	38.9422	63.6385	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	51.7000	31.85762	4.50535	42.6462	60.7538	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	19	67.3684	15.75581	3.61463	59.7744	74.9625	35.00	90.00
	Tim	31	70.9677	18.50312	3.32326	64.1807	77.7547	30.00	100.00
	Total	50	69.6000	17.43325	2.46543	64.6455	74.5545	30.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	19	62.6316	25.07591	5.75281	50.5454	74.7178	5.00	100.00
	Tim	31	59.0323	29.84458	5.36024	48.0852	69.9793	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	60.4000	27.91825	3.94824	52.4657	68.3343	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	19	63.0000	14.00837	3.21374	56.2482	69.7518	39.00	94.67
	Tim	31	63.9032	22.08489	3.96656	55.8024	72.0040	23.67	100.00
	Total	50	63.5600	19.25876	2.72360	58.0867	69.0333	23.67	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Motivation facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.046	1	47.999	.048
Recall	Welch	.419	1	42.940	.521
FMeasure	Welch	.066	1	47.521	.798
Duration	Welch	2.384	1	29.925	.133
FirstActDet	Welch	.099	1	36.548	.755
LastActDet	Welch	3.269	1	23.764	.083
ProcDur	Welch	.913	1	38.223	.345
FixRel	Welch	.330	1	38.315	.569
FixIrrel	Welch	.305	1	42.911	.583
AvDurRelFix	Welch	.002	1	37.104	.963
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.114	1	38.005	.298
TotSac	Welch	.232	1	39.986	.632
Sac2Key	Welch	1.160	1	47.071	.287
AvAttention	Welch	.709	1	40.371	.405
AvMentWL	Welch	.009	1	37.221	.925
AvFam	Welch	.917	1	35.388	.345
AvSCL	Welch	.050	1	35.649	.825
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.496	1	39.747	.485
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.424	1	40.045	.519
NASA_MD	Welch	.322	1	47.166	.573
NASA_PD	Welch	.485	1	37.901	.490
NASA_TD	Welch	.609	1	46.588	.439
NASA_Performance	Welch	.014	1	42.058	.906
NASA_Effort	Welch	.537	1	42.900	.468
NASA_Frustration	Welch	.210	1	43.258	.649
NASA_Score	Welch	.031	1	47.907	.860

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Information processing facet									
		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	39	.6256	.21676	.03471	.5554	.6959	.00	1.00
	Tim	11	.3749	.22802	.06875	.2217	.5281	.00	.67
	Total	50	.5705	.24095	.03408	.5020	.6389	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	39	.6833	.25724	.04119	.5999	.7667	.00	1.00
	Tim	11	.5951	.39924	.12038	.3269	.8633	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6639	.29191	.04128	.5809	.7469	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	39	.6129	.18517	.02965	.5528	.6729	.00	1.00
	Tim	11	.4429	.27802	.08382	.2561	.6297	.00	.76
	Total	50	.5755	.21777	.03080	.5136	.6374	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	39	1188.1795	588.24797	94.19506	997.4916	1378.8674	543.00	2650.00
	Tim	11	1644.9091	820.84425	247.49386	1093.4584	2196.3598	863.00	2605.00
	Total	50	1288.6600	665.12256	94.06254	1099.6343	1477.6857	543.00	2650.00
FirstActDet	Abby	39	154.8205	117.69114	18.84566	116.6695	192.9716	50.00	455.00
	Tim	11	211.3636	166.34258	50.15418	99.6132	323.1141	50.00	540.00
	Total	50	167.2600	130.18634	18.41113	130.2615	204.2585	50.00	540.00
LastActDet	Abby	39	772.7436	473.77669	75.86499	619.1630	926.3242	234.00	2005.00
	Tim	11	1569.2727	864.02281	260.51268	988.8143	2149.7311	587.00	2600.00
	Total	50	947.9800	661.45565	93.54395	759.9964	1135.9636	234.00	2600.00
ProcDur	Abby	39	415.4359	246.11131	39.40935	335.6558	495.2160	18.00	1072.00
	Tim	11	75.6364	119.35349	35.98643	-4.5464	155.8191	1.00	416.00
	Total	50	340.6800	264.76100	37.44286	265.4358	415.9242	1.00	1072.00
FixRel	Abby	39	1.6734	.63473	.10164	1.4677	1.8792	.65	2.60
	Tim	11	1.3123	.62820	.18941	.8903	1.7343	.50	2.60
	Total	50	1.5940	.64484	.09119	1.4107	1.7772	.50	2.60
FixIrrel	Abby	39	5.1105	4.35044	.69663	3.7002	6.5207	.07	15.20
	Tim	11	.2531	.35615	.10738	.0139	.4924	.06	1.26
	Total	50	4.0419	4.33991	.61376	2.8085	5.2753	.06	15.20
AvDurRelFix	Abby	39	379.2068	273.12324	43.73472	290.6705	467.7431	47.00	1417.86
	Tim	11	835.2615	397.55649	119.86779	568.1794	1102.3436	249.71	1567.33
	Total	50	479.5389	355.70251	50.30393	378.4493	580.6284	47.00	1567.33
AvDurIrrelFix	Abby	39	704.5459	454.02602	72.70235	557.3677	851.7241	149.87	1817.39
	Tim	11	309.6350	341.01089	102.81865	80.5408	538.7293	26.48	1206.22
	Total	50	617.6655	459.24251	64.94670	487.1502	748.1808	26.48	1817.39
TotSac	Abby	39	59.3590	12.12107	1.94092	55.4298	63.2882	40.00	79.00
	Tim	11	64.3636	11.25409	3.39324	56.8030	71.9242	44.00	79.00
	Total	50	60.4600	12.00716	1.69807	57.0476	63.8724	40.00	79.00
Sac2Key	Abby	39	28.8718	10.19850	1.63307	25.5658	32.1778	15.00	55.00
	Tim	11	30.6364	10.95694	3.30364	23.2754	37.9973	15.00	52.00
	Total	50	29.2600	10.28137	1.45401	26.3381	32.1819	15.00	55.00
AvAttention	Abby	39	.7205	.16251	.02602	.6678	.7732	.50	1.00
	Tim	11	.4727	.17939	.05409	.3522	.5932	.30	.80
	Total	50	.6660	.19442	.02750	.6107	.7213	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	39	.7205	.18804	.03011	.6596	.7815	.30	1.00
	Tim	11	.5636	.19633	.05920	.4317	.6955	.30	.90
	Total	50	.6860	.19899	.02814	.6294	.7426	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	39	.3744	.14994	.02401	.3258	.4230	.10	.60
	Tim	11	.4455	.15076	.04545	.3442	.5467	.20	.60
	Total	50	.3900	.15152	.02143	.3469	.4331	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	39	790.5897	134.14107	21.47976	747.1062	834.0732	503.00	998.00
	Tim	11	756.7273	161.84752	48.79886	647.9966	865.4579	510.00	933.00
	Total	50	783.1400	139.64606	19.74893	743.4530	822.8270	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	39	64.1681	22.02918	3.52749	37.0271	51.3092	10.92	82.27
	Tim	11	43.7943	17.99318	5.42515	31.7063	55.8823	24.97	75.96
	Total	50	54.0312	20.01118	4.47632	44.3667	53.5957	18.45	79.11

	Total	50	44.0859	21.03426	2.97469	38.1080	50.0637	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	39	27.2303	20.88058	3.34357	20.4616	33.9990	.10	60.08
	Tim	11	24.5504	17.36796	5.23664	12.8824	36.2183	3.81	56.57
	Total	50	26.6407	20.02347	2.83175	20.9501	32.3313	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	39	76.5385	18.60793	2.97965	70.5065	82.5705	20.00	100.00
	Tim	11	73.1818	7.16684	2.16088	68.3671	77.9966	65.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.8000	16.76245	2.37057	71.0362	80.5638	20.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	39	24.8718	21.65784	3.46803	17.8511	31.8925	5.00	70.00
	Tim	11	34.5455	22.52272	6.79085	19.4145	49.6764	5.00	65.00
	Total	50	27.0000	21.99258	3.11022	20.7498	33.2502	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	39	47.6923	27.50230	4.40389	38.7771	56.6075	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	35.4545	18.22835	5.49605	23.2086	47.7005	5.00	60.00
	Total	50	45.0000	26.08855	3.68948	37.5857	52.4143	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	39	54.6154	30.78757	4.92996	44.6352	64.5956	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	41.3636	34.93500	10.53330	17.8940	64.8333	5.00	85.00
	Total	50	51.7000	31.85762	4.50535	42.6462	60.7538	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	39	70.1282	18.96975	3.03759	63.9789	76.2775	30.00	100.00
	Tim	11	67.7273	10.80825	3.25881	60.4662	74.9884	55.00	90.00
	Total	50	69.6000	17.43325	2.46543	64.6455	74.5545	30.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	39	65.0000	24.22482	3.87908	57.1472	72.8528	5.00	100.00
	Tim	11	44.0909	34.84381	10.50580	20.6825	67.4993	5.00	90.00
	Total	50	60.4000	27.91825	3.94824	52.4657	68.3343	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	39	65.6923	19.68931	3.15281	59.3098	72.0748	23.67	100.00
	Tim	11	56.0000	16.23782	4.89589	45.0913	66.9087	39.00	83.67
	Total	50	63.5600	19.25876	2.72360	58.0867	69.0333	23.67	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Information processing facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	10.600	1	15.483	.005
Recall	Welch	.480	1	12.434	.501
FMeasure	Welch	3.654	1	12.607	.079
Duration	Welch	2.975	1	13.035	.108
FirstActDet	Welch	1.114	1	12.955	.311
LastActDet	Welch	8.618	1	11.746	.013
ProcDur	Welch	40.540	1	35.088	.000
FixRel	Welch	2.822	1	16.234	.112
FixIrrel	Welch	47.490	1	39.742	.000
AvDurRelFix	Welch	12.775	1	12.780	.003
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	9.835	1	21.111	.005
TotSac	Welch	1.639	1	17.132	.218
Sac2Key	Welch	.229	1	15.245	.639
AvAttention	Welch	17.042	1	14.954	.001
AvMentWL	Welch	5.580	1	15.570	.032
AvFam	Welch	1.913	1	16.031	.186
AvSCL	Welch	.403	1	14.111	.536
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.003	1	19.333	.045
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.186	1	18.985	.671
NASA_MD	Welch	.832	1	43.139	.367
NASA_PD	Welch	1.609	1	15.617	.223
NASA_TD	Welch	3.019	1	24.325	.095
NASA_Performance	Welch	1.298	1	14.676	.273
NASA_Effort	Welch	.290	1	29.137	.594
NASA_Frustration	Welch	3.486	1	12.850	.085
NASA_Score	Welch	2.770	1	19.147	.112

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Self-efficacy facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	32	.6211	.22629	.04000	.5395	.7027	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.4804	.24606	.05800	.3581	.6028	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.5705	.24095	.03408	.5020	.6389	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	32	.6726	.26103	.04614	.5785	.7667	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.6484	.34779	.08197	.4755	.8214	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6639	.29191	.04128	.5809	.7469	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	32	.6089	.19745	.03491	.5378	.6801	.00	1.00
	Tim	18	.5160	.24442	.05761	.3945	.6375	.00	.80
	Total	50	.5755	.21777	.03080	.5136	.6374	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	32	1086.6875	571.19170	100.97338	880.7509	1292.6241	543.00	2650.00
	Tim	18	1647.7222	683.28444	161.05169	1307.9329	1987.5116	863.00	2605.00
	Total	50	1288.6600	665.12256	94.06254	1099.6343	1477.6857	543.00	2650.00
FirstActDet	Abby	32	165.4375	127.73333	22.58028	119.3847	211.4903	50.00	455.00
	Tim	18	170.5000	138.13687	32.55917	101.8062	239.1938	50.00	540.00
	Total	50	167.2600	130.18634	18.41113	130.2615	204.2585	50.00	540.00
LastActDet	Abby	32	672.5625	406.85568	71.92260	525.8754	819.2496	234.00	2005.00
	Tim	18	1437.6111	750.07954	176.79544	1064.6053	1810.6169	564.00	2600.00
	Total	50	947.9800	661.45565	93.54395	759.9964	1135.9636	234.00	2600.00
ProcDur	Abby	32	414.1250	254.96436	45.07176	322.2005	506.0495	18.00	1072.00
	Tim	18	210.1111	235.16299	55.42845	93.1673	327.0549	1.00	620.00
	Total	50	340.6800	264.76100	37.44286	265.4358	415.9242	1.00	1072.00
FixRel	Abby	32	1.6110	.59027	.10435	1.3981	1.8238	.89	2.60
	Tim	18	1.5638	.74945	.17665	1.1911	1.9365	.50	2.60
	Total	50	1.5940	.64484	.09119	1.4107	1.7772	.50	2.60
FixIrrel	Abby	32	5.3601	4.67812	.82698	3.6734	7.0467	.07	15.20
	Tim	18	1.6984	2.30110	.54238	.5541	2.8427	.06	7.89
	Total	50	4.0419	4.33991	.61376	2.8085	5.2753	.06	15.20
AvDurRelFix	Abby	32	347.5155	279.47962	49.40548	246.7523	448.2786	47.00	1417.86
	Tim	18	714.2471	362.09896	85.34754	534.1795	894.3147	247.57	1567.33
	Total	50	479.5389	355.70251	50.30393	378.4493	580.6284	47.00	1567.33
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	32	684.1495	457.57950	80.88939	519.1745	849.1245	149.87	1642.04
	Tim	18	499.4718	450.53121	106.19122	275.4279	723.5157	26.48	1817.39
	Total	50	617.6655	459.24251	64.94670	487.1502	748.1808	26.48	1817.39
TotSac	Abby	32	58.1250	12.56660	2.22148	53.5943	62.6557	40.00	78.00
	Tim	18	64.6111	9.95365	2.34610	59.6613	69.5609	44.00	79.00
	Total	50	60.4600	12.00716	1.69807	57.0476	63.8724	40.00	79.00
Sac2Key	Abby	32	29.2188	11.05334	1.95397	25.2336	33.2039	15.00	55.00
	Tim	18	29.3333	9.04889	2.13284	24.8334	33.8332	15.00	52.00
	Total	50	29.2600	10.28137	1.45401	26.3381	32.1819	15.00	55.00
AvAttention	Abby	32	.7406	.16236	.02870	.6821	.7992	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.5333	.17823	.04201	.4447	.6220	.30	.80
	Total	50	.6660	.19442	.02750	.6107	.7213	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	32	.7563	.16837	.02976	.6955	.8170	.50	1.00
	Tim	18	.5611	.19140	.04511	.4659	.6563	.30	.90
	Total	50	.6860	.19899	.02814	.6294	.7426	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	32	.3938	.14797	.02616	.3404	.4471	.10	.60
	Tim	18	.3833	.16179	.03813	.3029	.4638	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3900	.15152	.02143	.3469	.4331	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	32	786.8750	127.16759	22.48027	741.0262	832.7238	503.00	998.00
	Tim	18	776.5000	163.23756	38.47546	695.3239	857.6761	510.00	963.00
	Total	50	783.1400	139.64606	19.74893	743.4530	822.8270	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	32	45.5393	22.03466	3.89522	37.5950	53.4837	10.92	82.27
	Tim	18	41.5019	19.46408	4.58773	31.8227	51.1812	10.92	82.27

	Total	50	44.0859	21.03426	2.97469	38.1080	50.0637	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	32	26.0083	20.62388	3.64582	18.5725	33.4440	.10	56.57
	Tim	18	27.7651	19.44038	4.58214	18.0976	37.4325	2.81	60.08
	Total	50	26.6407	20.02347	2.83175	20.9501	32.3313	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	32	77.6563	19.71508	3.48517	70.5482	84.7643	20.00	100.00
	Tim	18	72.5000	9.11527	2.14849	67.9671	77.0329	50.00	90.00
	Total	50	75.8000	16.76245	2.37057	71.0362	80.5638	20.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	32	25.9375	22.12273	3.91078	17.9614	33.9136	5.00	70.00
	Tim	18	28.8889	22.26548	5.24802	17.8165	39.9613	5.00	65.00
	Total	50	27.0000	21.99258	3.11022	20.7498	33.2502	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	32	46.4063	28.54635	5.04633	36.1142	56.6983	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	42.5000	21.57409	5.08506	31.7715	53.2285	5.00	90.00
	Total	50	45.0000	26.08855	3.68948	37.5857	52.4143	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	32	55.7813	30.77256	5.43987	44.6866	66.8759	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	44.4444	33.33823	7.85790	27.8657	61.0232	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	51.7000	31.85762	4.50535	42.6462	60.7538	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	32	70.9375	19.61063	3.46670	63.8671	78.0079	30.00	100.00
	Tim	18	67.2222	12.85922	3.03095	60.8275	73.6170	35.00	90.00
	Total	50	69.6000	17.43325	2.46543	64.6455	74.5545	30.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	32	64.5313	25.53806	4.51453	55.3238	73.7387	5.00	100.00
	Tim	18	53.0556	31.11359	7.33354	37.5831	68.5280	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	60.4000	27.91825	3.94824	52.4657	68.3343	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	32	66.4688	20.54087	3.63115	59.0630	73.8745	23.67	100.00
	Tim	18	58.3889	15.98212	3.76702	50.4412	66.3366	39.00	94.67
	Total	50	63.5600	19.25876	2.72360	58.0867	69.0333	23.67	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Self-efficacy facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	3.988	1	32.935	.045
Recall	Welch	.066	1	27.942	.799
FMeasure	Welch	1.904	1	29.586	.178
Duration	Welch	8.711	1	30.414	.006
FirstActDet	Welch	.016	1	33.088	.899
LastActDet	Welch	16.067	1	22.751	.001
ProcDur	Welch	8.155	1	37.841	.007
FixRel	Welch	.053	1	28.997	.820
FixIrrel	Welch	13.709	1	47.409	.001
AvDurRelFix	Welch	13.829	1	28.544	.001
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	1.914	1	35.835	.018
TotSac	Welch	4.030	1	42.441	.051
Sac2Key	Welch	.002	1	41.486	.969
AvAttention	Welch	16.600	1	32.672	.000
AvMentWL	Welch	13.036	1	31.723	.001
AvFam	Welch	.051	1	32.781	.823
AvSCL	Welch	.054	1	28.751	.818
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	.450	1	39.179	.506
HRVar_NN50	Welch	.090	1	37.169	.766
NASA_MD	Welch	1.586	1	46.732	.214
NASA_PD	Welch	.203	1	35.175	.655
NASA_TD	Welch	.297	1	43.719	.588
NASA_Performance	Welch	1.407	1	33.038	.244
NASA_Effort	Welch	.651	1	46.723	.424
NASA_Frustration	Welch	1.776	1	29.966	.193
NASA_Score	Welch	2.385	1	42.939	.130

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Risk facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	14	.7656	.24818	.06633	.6224	.9089	.21	1.00
	Tim	36	.4946	.19297	.03216	.4293	.5599	.00	.86
	Total	50	.5705	.24095	.03408	.5020	.6389	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	14	.6521	.28265	.07554	.4889	.8153	.10	1.00
	Tim	36	.6685	.29924	.04987	.5672	.7697	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6639	.29191	.04128	.5809	.7469	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	14	.6653	.23662	.06324	.5287	.8019	.14	1.00
	Tim	36	.5406	.20277	.03380	.4720	.6092	.00	.80
	Total	50	.5755	.21777	.03080	.5136	.6374	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	14	1622.7857	918.44728	245.46536	1092.4900	2153.0814	543.00	2650.00
	Tim	36	1158.7222	493.96776	82.32796	991.5876	1325.8569	601.00	2075.00
	Total	50	1288.6600	665.12256	94.06254	1099.6343	1477.6857	543.00	2650.00
FirstActDet	Abby	14	268.8571	160.80751	42.97761	176.0097	361.7046	82.00	540.00
	Tim	36	127.7500	91.58957	15.26493	96.7605	158.7395	50.00	436.00
	Total	50	167.2600	130.18634	18.41113	130.2615	204.2585	50.00	540.00
LastActDet	Abby	14	1317.2143	960.15906	256.61330	762.8350	1871.5936	234.00	2600.00
	Tim	36	804.3889	440.87402	73.47900	655.2186	953.5592	234.00	2003.00
	Total	50	947.9800	661.45565	93.54395	759.9964	1135.9636	234.00	2600.00
ProcDur	Abby	14	305.5714	288.14866	77.01097	139.1993	471.9435	5.00	1072.00
	Tim	36	354.3333	258.09566	43.01594	267.0063	441.6603	1.00	985.00
	Total	50	340.6800	264.76100	37.44286	265.4358	415.9242	1.00	1072.00
FixRel	Abby	14	1.5889	.69014	.18445	1.1904	1.9874	.65	2.60
	Tim	36	1.5960	.63657	.10609	1.3806	1.8113	.50	2.60
	Total	50	1.5940	.64484	.09119	1.4107	1.7772	.50	2.60
FixIrrel	Abby	14	4.4068	5.20842	1.39201	1.3995	7.4140	.06	15.20
	Tim	36	3.9000	4.02726	.67121	2.5373	5.2626	.06	15.20
	Total	50	4.0419	4.33991	.61376	2.8085	5.2753	.06	15.20
AvDurRelFix	Abby	14	626.9605	479.35531	128.11310	350.1890	903.7321	75.29	1567.33
	Tim	36	422.2082	282.33418	47.05570	326.6801	517.7363	47.00	1295.73
	Total	50	479.5389	355.70251	50.30393	378.4493	580.6284	47.00	1567.33
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	14	584.3257	402.51318	107.57617	351.9215	816.7299	149.87	1600.27
	Tim	36	630.6310	484.22096	80.70349	466.7942	794.4678	26.48	1817.39
	Total	50	617.6655	459.24251	64.94670	487.1502	748.1808	26.48	1817.39
TotSac	Abby	14	60.2857	11.51874	3.07851	53.6350	66.9364	41.00	77.00
	Tim	36	60.5278	12.35079	2.05847	56.3489	64.7067	40.00	79.00
	Total	50	60.4600	12.00716	1.69807	57.0476	63.8724	40.00	79.00
Sac2Key	Abby	14	29.5000	11.68003	3.12162	22.7562	36.2438	15.00	55.00
	Tim	36	29.1667	9.86335	1.64389	25.8294	32.5039	15.00	52.00
	Total	50	29.2600	10.28137	1.45401	26.3381	32.1819	15.00	55.00
AvAttention	Abby	14	.6786	.21901	.05853	.5521	.8050	.30	1.00
	Tim	36	.6611	.18713	.03119	.5978	.7244	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6660	.19442	.02750	.6107	.7213	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	14	.6714	.18576	.04965	.5642	.7787	.40	1.00
	Tim	36	.6917	.20616	.03436	.6219	.7614	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6860	.19899	.02814	.6294	.7426	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	14	.4214	.14239	.03806	.3392	.5036	.20	.60
	Tim	36	.3778	.15512	.02585	.3253	.4303	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3900	.15152	.02143	.3469	.4331	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	14	786.7143	151.85440	40.58480	699.0362	874.3924	520.00	998.00
	Tim	36	781.7500	136.85495	22.80916	735.4449	828.0551	503.00	963.00
	Total	50	783.1400	139.64606	19.74893	743.4530	822.8270	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	14	32.3072	15.49325	4.14075	23.3617	41.2528	14.62	75.96
	Tim	36	48.6665	21.28807	3.54801	41.4636	55.8693	10.92	82.27
	Total	50	40.4869	18.44066	2.94438	35.4459	45.8661	12.77	79.12

	Total	50	44.0859	21.03426	2.97469	38.1080	50.0637	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	14	18.8129	16.70907	4.46569	9.1654	28.4605	1.18	56.57
	Tim	36	29.6848	20.58091	3.43015	22.7213	36.6484	.10	60.08
	Total	50	26.6407	20.02347	2.83175	20.9501	32.3313	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	14	77.1429	22.67787	6.06092	64.0490	90.2367	20.00	100.00
	Tim	36	75.2778	14.18976	2.36496	70.4767	80.0789	20.00	100.00
	Total	50	75.8000	16.76245	2.37057	71.0362	80.5638	20.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	14	37.5000	27.36857	7.31456	21.6979	53.3021	10.00	70.00
	Tim	36	22.9167	18.37603	3.06267	16.6991	29.1342	5.00	70.00
	Total	50	27.0000	21.99258	3.11022	20.7498	33.2502	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	14	63.5714	30.97322	8.27794	45.6880	81.4548	25.00	100.00
	Tim	36	37.7778	20.12264	3.35377	30.9693	44.5863	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	45.0000	26.08855	3.68948	37.5857	52.4143	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	14	72.1429	33.43848	8.93681	52.8361	91.4497	5.00	100.00
	Tim	36	43.7500	27.80994	4.63499	34.3405	53.1595	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	51.7000	31.85762	4.50535	42.6462	60.7538	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	14	69.2857	22.51983	6.01868	56.2832	82.2883	30.00	100.00
	Tim	36	69.7222	15.39687	2.56614	64.5127	74.9318	30.00	100.00
	Total	50	69.6000	17.43325	2.46543	64.6455	74.5545	30.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	14	75.0000	30.44541	8.13688	57.4213	92.5787	5.00	100.00
	Tim	36	54.7222	25.06974	4.17829	46.2398	63.2046	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	60.4000	27.91825	3.94824	52.4657	68.3343	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	14	74.0238	24.38069	6.51601	59.9468	88.1008	23.67	100.00
	Tim	36	59.4907	15.41582	2.56930	54.2748	64.7067	23.67	100.00
	Total	50	63.5600	19.25876	2.72360	58.0867	69.0333	23.67	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Risk facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	13.523	1	19.433	.002
Recall	Welch	.033	1	25.036	.858
FMeasure	Welch	3.025	1	20.854	.097
Duration	Welch	3.213	1	16.014	.092
FirstActDet	Welch	9.572	1	16.390	.007
LastActDet	Welch	3.691	1	15.181	.074
ProcDur	Welch	.306	1	21.597	.586
FixRel	Welch	.001	1	22.126	.974
FixIrrel	Welch	.108	1	19.359	.746
AvDurRelFix	Welch	2.251	1	16.632	.152
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	.119	1	28.408	.733
TotSac	Welch	.004	1	25.342	.948
Sac2Key	Welch	.009	1	20.621	.926
AvAttention	Welch	.069	1	20.806	.795
AvMentWL	Welch	.112	1	26.203	.740
AvFam	Welch	.900	1	25.734	.352
AvSCL	Welch	.011	1	21.705	.916
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	9.001	1	32.575	.005
HRVar_NN50	Welch	3.728	1	29.102	.063
NASA_MD	Welch	.082	1	17.113	.778
NASA_PD	Welch	3.382	1	17.755	.083
NASA_TD	Welch	8.340	1	17.443	.070
NASA_Performance	Welch	7.954	1	20.386	.060
NASA_Effort	Welch	.004	1	17.936	.948
NASA_Frustration	Welch	4.915	1	20.237	.058
NASA_Score	Welch	4.305	1	17.202	.053

a. Asymptotically F distributed.

Descriptives - Learning style facet

		N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	95% Confidence Interval for Mean		Minimum	Maximum
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound		
Precision	Abby	12	.6120	.23147	.06682	.4649	.7591	.21	1.00
	Tim	38	.5573	.24540	.03981	.4767	.6380	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.5705	.24095	.03408	.5020	.6389	.00	1.00
Recall	Abby	12	.6844	.28754	.08301	.5017	.8671	.10	1.00
	Tim	38	.6574	.29679	.04815	.5599	.7550	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.6639	.29191	.04128	.5809	.7469	.00	1.00
FMeasure	Abby	12	.6105	.21410	.06181	.4745	.7466	.14	1.00
	Tim	38	.5644	.22057	.03578	.4919	.6369	.00	1.00
	Total	50	.5755	.21777	.03080	.5136	.6374	.00	1.00
Duration	Abby	12	1288.0000	758.31752	218.90741	1506.1880	2469.8120	708.00	2650.00
	Tim	38	1067.8158	454.08815	73.66282	918.5607	1217.0708	543.00	2075.00
	Total	50	1288.6600	665.12256	94.06254	1099.6343	1477.6857	543.00	2650.00
FirstActDet	Abby	12	383.5833	71.29893	20.58223	338.2822	428.8845	300.00	540.00
	Tim	38	98.9474	31.05179	5.03726	88.7409	109.1538	50.00	215.00
	Total	50	167.2600	130.18634	18.41113	130.2615	204.2585	50.00	540.00
LastActDet	Abby	12	1565.0000	860.68017	248.45697	1018.1499	2111.8501	423.00	2600.00
	Tim	38	753.1316	443.53958	71.95162	607.3437	898.9194	234.00	2003.00
	Total	50	947.9800	661.45565	93.54395	759.9964	1135.9636	234.00	2600.00
ProcDur	Abby	12	423.0000	389.07630	112.31665	175.7927	670.2073	5.00	1072.00
	Tim	38	314.6842	211.98153	34.38794	245.0076	384.3608	1.00	985.00
	Total	50	340.6800	264.76100	37.44286	265.4358	415.9242	1.00	1072.00
FixRel	Abby	12	1.5497	.61261	.17685	1.1605	1.9390	.65	2.60
	Tim	38	1.6080	.66202	.10739	1.3904	1.8256	.50	2.60
	Total	50	1.5940	2.84148	.09119	1.4107	1.7772	.50	2.60
FixIrrel	Abby	12	4.5590	4.62586	.75041	3.0385	6.0795	.06	15.20
	Tim	38	2.4042	2.84148	.82027	.5988	4.2096	.06	8.56
	Total	50	4.0419	4.33991	.61376	2.8085	5.2753	.06	15.20
AvDurRelFix	Abby	12	424.1777	274.55235	44.53827	333.9346	514.4208	47.00	1295.73
	Tim	38	654.8492	515.69878	148.86941	327.1898	982.5086	75.29	1567.33
	Total	50	479.5389	355.70251	50.30393	378.4493	580.6284	47.00	1567.33
AvDurlrrelFix	Abby	12	812.6570	547.57801	158.07216	464.7425	1160.5715	180.07	1642.04
	Tim	38	556.0893	417.05790	67.65572	419.0057	693.1728	26.48	1817.39
	Total	50	617.6655	459.24251	64.94670	487.1502	748.1808	26.48	1817.39
TotSac	Abby	12	59.0833	13.56103	3.91473	50.4671	67.6996	40.00	78.00
	Tim	38	60.8947	11.63822	1.88797	57.0694	64.7201	40.00	79.00
	Total	50	60.4600	12.00716	1.69807	57.0476	63.8724	40.00	79.00
Sac2Key	Abby	12	30.7500	11.80235	3.40704	23.2511	38.2489	15.00	50.00
	Tim	38	28.7895	9.88080	1.60288	25.5417	32.0372	15.00	55.00
	Total	50	29.2600	10.28137	1.45401	26.3381	32.1819	15.00	55.00
AvAttention	Abby	12	.7000	.24863	.07177	.5420	.8580	.30	1.00
	Tim	38	.6553	.17660	.02865	.5972	.7133	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6660	.19442	.02750	.6107	.7213	.30	1.00
AvMentWL	Abby	12	.6583	.15050	.04345	.5627	.7540	.40	.90
	Tim	38	.6947	.21302	.03456	.6247	.7648	.30	1.00
	Total	50	.6860	.19899	.02814	.6294	.7426	.30	1.00
AvFam	Abby	12	.4333	.13707	.03957	.3462	.5204	.20	.60
	Tim	38	.3763	.15498	.02514	.3254	.4273	.10	.60
	Total	50	.3900	.15152	.02143	.3469	.4331	.10	.60
AvSCL	Abby	12	801.1667	150.41508	43.42109	705.5975	896.7359	520.00	998.00
	Tim	38	777.4474	137.69800	22.33757	732.1872	822.7076	503.00	963.00
	Total	50	783.1400	139.64606	19.74893	743.4530	822.8270	503.00	998.00
HRVar_RMSSD	Abby	12	33.9923	20.52405	5.92478	20.9519	47.0326	10.92	75.96
	Tim	38	47.2733	20.42607	3.31355	40.5595	53.9872	10.92	82.27

	Total	50	44.0859	21.03426	2.97469	38.1080	50.0637	10.92	82.27
HRVar_NN50	Abby	12	17.7743	18.51538	5.34493	6.0102	29.5384	.10	53.47
	Tim	38	29.4406	19.88736	3.22616	22.9038	35.9774	1.18	60.08
	Total	50	26.6407	20.02347	2.83175	20.9501	32.3313	.10	60.08
NASA_MD	Abby	12	74.1667	23.14316	6.68086	59.4622	88.8711	20.00	100.00
	Tim	38	76.3158	14.55113	2.36051	71.5330	81.0986	20.00	100.00
	Total	50	75.8000	16.76245	2.37057	71.0362	80.5638	20.00	100.00
NASA_PD	Abby	12	37.5000	26.41453	7.62522	20.7170	54.2830	10.00	70.00
	Tim	38	23.6842	19.64840	3.18739	17.2259	30.1425	5.00	70.00
	Total	50	27.0000	21.99258	3.11022	20.7498	33.2502	5.00	70.00
NASA_TD	Abby	12	55.8333	28.67001	8.27632	37.6173	74.0494	25.00	100.00
	Tim	38	41.5789	24.63532	3.99638	33.4815	49.6764	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	45.0000	26.08855	3.68948	37.5857	52.4143	5.00	100.00
NASA_Performance	Abby	12	66.2500	32.96865	9.51723	45.3027	87.1973	5.00	100.00
	Tim	38	47.1053	30.50546	4.94864	37.0784	57.1322	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	51.7000	31.85762	4.50535	42.6462	60.7538	5.00	100.00
NASA_Effort	Abby	12	66.6667	22.89634	6.60960	52.1190	81.2143	30.00	100.00
	Tim	38	70.5263	15.58713	2.52857	65.4030	75.6497	30.00	100.00
	Total	50	69.6000	17.43325	2.46543	64.6455	74.5545	30.00	100.00
NASA_Frustration	Abby	12	69.5833	30.03470	8.67027	50.5002	88.6665	5.00	100.00
	Tim	38	57.5000	26.98223	4.37710	48.6312	66.3688	5.00	100.00
	Total	50	60.4000	27.91825	3.94824	52.4657	68.3343	5.00	100.00
NASA_Score	Abby	12	68.8611	23.17673	6.69055	54.1353	83.5869	23.67	100.00
	Tim	38	61.8860	17.87465	2.89965	56.0107	67.7612	23.67	100.00
	Total	50	63.5600	19.25876	2.72360	58.0867	69.0333	23.67	100.00

Robust Tests of Equality of Means - Learning style facet

		Statistic ^a	df1	df2	Sig.
Precision	Welch	.494	1	19.466	.491
Recall	Welch	.079	1	19.007	.781
FMeasure	Welch	.417	1	18.975	.526
Duration	Welch	15.872	1	13.580	.061
FirstActDet	Welch	180.439	1	12.344	.051
LastActDet	Welch	9.851	1	12.895	.068
ProcDur	Welch	.850	1	13.125	.373
FixRel	Welch	.079	1	19.808	.781
FixIrrel	Welch	3.757	1	30.720	.042
AvDurRelFix	Welch	2.204	1	13.026	.036
AvDurIrrelFix	Welch	2.227	1	15.247	.046
TotSac	Welch	.174	1	16.447	.682
Sac2Key	Welch	.271	1	16.173	.610
AvAttention	Welch	.335	1	14.673	.571
AvMentWL	Welch	.430	1	26.202	.518
AvFam	Welch	1.479	1	20.673	.238
AvSCL	Welch	.236	1	17.234	.633
HRVar_RMSSD	Welch	3.828	1	18.422	.066
HRVar_NN50	Welch	3.492	1	19.698	.077
NASA_MD	Welch	.092	1	13.854	.766
NASA_PD	Welch	2.795	1	15.043	.115
NASA_TD	Welch	2.405	1	16.462	.140
NASA_Performance	Welch	3.185	1	17.375	.092
NASA_Effort	Welch	.297	1	14.364	.594
NASA_Frustration	Welch	1.548	1	16.993	.230
NASA_Score	Welch	.915	1	15.359	.354

a. Asymptotically F distributed.